

**STABILITY INDICATING RP-HPLC METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND
VALIDATION FOR THE SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF SAXAGLIPTIN AND
DAPAGLIFLOZIN IN BULK AND ITS DOSAGE FORM**

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ABSTRACT

A stability indicating RP-HPLC method for the simultaneous determination of Saxagliptin and Dapagliflozin has been developed and validated in bulk and injection dosage form. The fixed dose combination of saxagliptin and Dapagliflozin is a recently approved antidiabetic medication. It is marketed under the brand name Q tern. The chromatographic analysis was performed on Xterra C18 (4.6*150mm, 5 μ) column with an isocratic mobile phase composed of 0.1% OPA: Methanol: Acetonitrile (30: 60: 10) at a flow rate of 1.0mL/min and the eluents were monitored at an is osbestic point of 225 nm. The developed method was validated according to the ICH guidelines pertaining to specificity, precision, accuracy, linearity and robustness. The stability indicating nature of the method was established by forced degradation studies. The retention time of Saxagliptin and Dapagliflozin was observed at 2.340 and 5.081 min respectively. The developed method proved to be accurate and precise. Linearity was established between 10to50 μ g/mL for Saxagliptin and between 20 and 100 μ g/mL for Dapagliflozin. The LOD and LOQ of Saxagliptin were found to be 0.57 and 1.89

$\mu\text{g/mL}$, for Dapagliflozin LOD and LOQ were found to be 3.02 and 10.07 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Therefore, the proposed HPLC method was reliable, reproducible, precise and sensitive for the quantification of Saxagliptin and Dapagliflozin.

Keywords: Saxagliptin, Dapagliflozin, HPLC method, stability indicating and validation.

INTRODUCTION

Type 2 diabetes mellitus is a chronic, progressive metabolic disorder marked by insulin insufficiency, either absolute or relative. [1,2] The expected growth in diabetes prevalence is mostly due to longer life expectancy as a result of improved healthcare facilities and an increase in diabetic risk factors, particularly physical inactivity and obesity as a result of a sedentary lifestyle.[3,4,5] In individuals with Type 2 diabetes, pancreatic β -cell activity deteriorates with time, resulting in poor glycemic control in the long term.[6]

The combination of saxagliptin with dapagliflozin has the potential to provide considerable glycaemic control advantages without the risk of weight gain or hypoglycemia associated with other type 2 diabetes medicines. [7] The US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) recently authorised a fixed dosage combination of 5 mg saxagliptin and 10 mg dapagliflozin for individuals with type 2 diabetes. Qtern was the brand name given to the combination. Saxagliptin is a kind of medication that inhibits the dipeptidyl-peptidase-4 enzyme. This type of substance stimulates glucose-dependent insulin secretion. In terms of chemistry, it is (1S,3S,5S)-2-((2S)-amino(3-hydroxytricyclo(3.3.1.1^{3,7})dec-1-yl)acetyl)-2-azabicyclo(3.1.0) hexane-3-carbonitrile (Figure 1a).[8] Dapagliflozin, is a sodium glucose co-transporter-2 inhibitor with the chemical name (2S,3R,4R,5S,6R)-2-[4-chloro-3-(4-ethoxybenzyl)phenyl]-6-(hydroxymethyl) tetrahydro-2H-pyran-3,4,5-triol (Figure 1b). [9]

Review of the literature revealed that a few analytical methods like LC-Mass spectrometry[10,11] HPLC[12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19] and spectroscopic methods[20,21] are available for the estimation of these drugs, either individually or in combination with other diabetic drugs like metformin.[22,23,24,25,26] The present work aimed to develop a simple, rapid, and accurate method for the estimation of saxagliptin and dapagliflozin in bulk and its tablets, as per ICH guidelines.[27,28]

However, existing LC methods were less convenient and time consuming, which were not suitable for routine individual and simultaneous estimation. The HPLC system reduces the time and significant costs of analyzing samples with better results. HPLC allows an analyst to work on superior skills with a much wider range of linear speeds, solvent flow rates and system back pressure than traditional HPLC. Considering the growing demand for the above titled drugs in global market, it is necessary to develop a new economic, accurate and rapid HPLC analytical technique for the simultaneous estimation of both drugs in the pharmaceutical formulation and to conduct forced degradation studies in five different conditions which could be applied to evaluate the quality, efficacy and storage conditions of each molecule.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemicals and reagents

Both drug standards were gifted from Pharma Train, Hyderabad, India. Methanol, water and acetonitrile (LC grade) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Analytical grade sodium hydroxide (NaOH), hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), hydrochloric acid (HCl) and a 0.22 mm membrane filter were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Qtern containing Saxagliptin and Dapagliflozin with the label claim of 5 mg and 10 mg respectively was purchased from the local pharmacy. All chemicals were analytical or LC grade.

HPLC instrumental condition

An Acquity HPLC system (Waters, Milford, MA, USA) equipped with a model 2995 PDA detector and Empower software was used to develop the method. The HPLC separation of the two drugs was obtained with an XterraC₁₈ analytical column (4.6 mm X 150 mm, 5µm) using 0.1% OPA: Methanol: Acetonitrile (30: 60: 10) in isocratic mode at a flow rate of 1mL/min and column at room temperature. The PDA detector was used to monitor the two drugs at 225 nm. The solvents were filtered on a 0.45 µm membrane filter and degassed in an ultrasonic bath before use. Mobile phase was used as diluent.

Preparation of working standard solution

Accurately weighed and transferred 10 mg of Saxagliptin and 20 mg of Dapagliflozin working standard into a 100 ml clean dry volumetric flask add about 70 mL of Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution). Further pipette 3.0 ml of the above stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent.

Analysis of formulations

A dose equivalent to 10 mg of Saxagliptin and 20 mg of Dapagliflozin from twenty tablets was weighed and transferred to a 100 ml volumetric flask. Then 70mL of diluent was added and sonicated to dissolve completely. Finally, the volume was made upto the mark with same solvent (primary formulation stock solution). Further, 3ml of the above solution was transferred to a standard 10 mL flask and diluted to the mark with the same solvent. Injected 20µL of into the HPLC system and measured the peak areas for Saxagliptin and Dapagliflozin and the percentage assay of the formulations was calculated.

Validation of chromatographic method

The developed method was validated as per the guidelines of ICH (ICH Guidelines, Q2 (R1), 2005).

System suitability

System suitability parameters were measured to verify system performance. The precision of the system was determined in six repeated injections of standard preparations. All important characteristics were measured, including the area of the peak, the resolution of the peaks and the theoretical plate number.

Accuracy(recovery)

Accuracy is represented (ICH Guidelines, Q2 (R1), 2005) and determined by recovery experiments. In this process, it was tested at three different levels that were 50, 100 and 150% and analyzed chromatogram.

Specificity

To assess the specificity, working placebo solution (blank) in the absence of the Saxagliptin and Dapagliflozin and standard, as well as formulations were introduced into the HPLC system and analyzed chromatograms.

Precision

Precision (Intraday and Inter day) of the analytical technique was proven by using optimized concentration of Saxagliptin and Dapagliflozin by six replicate injections. Average and % RSD of peak area was determined from chromatograms.

Linearity

Linearity was confirmed by preparing and analyzing the pure analytical standard preparation at five totally different concentrations. The developed method displays ideal linearity over a range of 10-50 µg/mL and 20-100 µg/mL for Saxagliptin and Dapagliflozin respectively.

Limit of detection (LOD) and Limit of quantitation (LOQ)

The LOD and LOQ of Saxagliptin and Dapagliflozin were determined by using signal to noise approach as defined in International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guideline

(ICH Guidelines, Q2 (R1), 2005). Increasingly dilute solution of each drug and impurity was injected into the chromatograph and signal to noise (S/N) ratio was calculated at each concentration.

Robustness

The robustness as a measure of method capacity to remain unaffected by small, but deliberate changes in chromatographic conditions was studied by testing influence of small changes in FTW change in flow rate (± 0.1 ml/min), change in mobile phase composition ($\pm 10\%$).

DEGRADATION STUDIES:

The International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guideline entitled stability testing of new drug substances and products requires that stress testing be carried out to elucidate the inherent stability characteristics of the active substance. The aim of this work was to perform the stress degradation studies on the Saxagliptin and Dapagliflozin using the proposed method.

Preparation of stock:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Saxagliptin and 20 mg of Dapagliflozin working standard into a 100 ml clean dry volumetric flask add about 7 mL of Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Hydrolytic degradation under acidic condition

Pipette 3 ml of above solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and 3 ml of 0.1N HCl was added. Then, the volumetric flask was kept at 60°C for 24 hours and then neutralized with 0.1 N NaOH and make up to 10ml with diluent. Filter the solution with 0.44 microns syringe filters and place in vials.

Hydrolytic degradation under alkaline condition

Pipette 3 ml of above solution into a 10ml volumetric and add 3ml of 0.1N NaOH was added in 10ml of volumetric flask. Then, the volumetric flask was kept at 60°C for 24 hours and then neutralized with 0.1N HCl and make up to 10ml with diluent. Filter the solution with 0.44 microns syringe filters and place in vials.

Thermal induced degradation

Saxagliptin and Dapagliflozin sample was taken in petridish and kept in Hot air oven at 110⁰ C for 3 hours. Then the sample was taken and diluted with diluents and injected into HPLC and analysed.

Oxidative degradation

Pipette 3 ml above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and 1ml of 30% w/v of hydrogen peroxide added in 10 ml of volumetric flask and the volume was made up to the mark with diluent. The volumetric flask was then kept at room temperature for 15 min. Filter the solution with 0.45 microns syringe filters and place in vials.

Photo degradation:

Pipette 3 ml above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and expose to sunlight for 24hrs and the volume was made up to the mark with diluent. Filter the solution with 0.45 microns syringe filters and place in vials.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Optimization of chromatographic conditions

Numerous trails have been performed based on the physico-chemical properties of the molecules. During the course of the trails, four reliable variables were taken into consideration, such as the stationary phase, the composition of the mobile phase, the flow rate and the column temperature. The trail was started by keeping one variable as constants and

modifying another variable. The ideal experimental design helps us to optimize chromatographic and robustness parameters. The HPLC resolution of the two drugs was achieved with a Xterra C₁₈ analytical column (4.6 mm X 150 mm, 5 μ m) using 0.1% OPA: Methanol: Acetonitrile (30: 60: 10) in isocratic mode at a flow rate of 1 mL/min and column at room temperature. The PDA detector was used to monitor the two drugs at 225 nm. The solvents were filtered on a 0.45 mm membrane filter and degassed in an ultrasonic bath before use. Mobile phase was used as diluent. Figure 2 (a-c) shows the blank, standard and sample chromatogram of Saxagliptin and Dapagliflozin.

Analysis of formulations

Marketed formulation was analyzed, and assay percentage was calculated. Results were obtained within ICH limit and summarized in Table 1.

Validation of HPLC Method

System suitability study

System suitability was attained by checking various parameters and found within the ICH limit. The results are presented in Table 2.

Accuracy (recovery)

Accuracy was ensured at three different levels that were 50, 100 and 150%. The results are shown in Table 3. Mean % Recoveries at 50, 100 and 150% for Dapagliflozin were found to be 100.39, 100.89 and 100.64 % respectively. Similarly for Saxagliptin 100.26, 100.20 and 100.61 at 50, 100 and 150% respectively.

Precision

Precision of the analytical method were established for both intra and interday by using optimized concentrations of Saxagliptin and Dapagliflozin six replicate injections. The results are shown in Table 4.

Specificity

The specificity of the technique was established that the chromatogram of the working placebo solution did not show any interference at the retention time of the Saxagliptin and Dapagliflozin. Thus, it can be concluded that main excipients that were present in the formulations as excipients does not interfere with the analytical method for the determinations of Saxagliptin and Dapagliflozin. The resulted chromatogram of blank, standard and formulation are shown in Figure2.

Linearity

The projected technique displays ideal linear over a range of 4.7, 7.05, 9.4, 11.75 and 14.1 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 0.05,0.075,0.1,0.125 and 0.15 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for Saxagliptin and Dapagliflozin respectively with excellent coefficient correlation more than 0.999 for both drugs. Residual plot of both drugs displays that residuals are randomly placed over, below and above the x-axis signifying that developed method is a linear model. The results are shown in table 5 and linearity curves were shown in figure 3.

Limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ)

The LOD and LOQ of Saxagliptin were found to be 0.57 and 1.89 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, for Dapagliflozin LOD and LOQ were found to be 3.02 and 10.07 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ respectively indicating that the method was extremely rapid and sensitive. Figure 4 shows the chromatograms of LOD and LOQ.

Robustness study

The study reveals that there was no much deviation in the robust chromatograms in assessment with optimized one. The results are shown in Table 6.

Forced degradation study

Degradation studies reveal the specificity of the developed method in the presence of degradation products that was carried in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form. It was

performed in combination of two drugs and purity of drug peaks was established by purity angles. The formulations were exposed to five different stress conditions.

In acidic and basic conditions, degradation may be due to catalysis of ionisable functional groups present in the drug molecule. The degradants were detected for basic and three for acidic condition, but not any more degrading peaks were reported in the retention time of the Saxagliptin and Dapagliflozin respectively. It was found that both drugs degrade more in acidic in comparison to an alkaline condition.

Two degradants were detected in the oxidative degradation study and not any degradant peaks were reported in the retention time of Saxagliptin and Dapagliflozin respectively. Saxagliptin undergoes more degradation than Dapagliflozin and degradation was up to 10.06% and 9.30% respectively. In photolytic stress conditions, it may be due to the photo oxidation by free radical mechanisms whereas in a thermal it can be explained on the basis of Arrhenius equation. The results are shortened in Table 7.

Even if unidentified peaks were observed in five different above stress conditions, not any degradants were found close to the retention time of Saxagliptin and Dapagliflozin respectively (Figure 5). Therefore Saxagliptin and Dapagliflozin are prone to the above stated condition and are too stable in the projected technique even in stress condition up to a specified period of time.

CONCLUSION

This technique was demonstrated to be quick, precise, selective, and robust and simple that may be applied to a latest FDA approved pharmaceutical combo of Saxagliptin and Dapagliflozin. This method of analysis could be applied for the safety, efficacy and quality of the drug in a cost effective manner. The established methods were validated as per ICH guideline and stability study revealed that the technique was useful in monitoring drug

stability. It could also be applied for routine analysis in Bioanalytical Laboratory, Hospital research institutions in therapeutic drug monitoring for clinical trials, in quality control division of pharmaceutical company, dissolution studies of the formulations and in accredited testing laboratories.

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Figure 1.Chemical structures of (a) Saxagliptin and (b) Dapagliflozin

Figure 4.(a) LOD and (b) LOQ Chromatograms of Saxagliptin and Dapagliflozin**Table 1.**Analysis of Formulation

Analytes	Mean Peak area*	% Assay*	%RSD*
Saxagliptin	56445	100.10	0.34
Dapagliflozin	320903	100.53	1.54

Mean of six replicates; % RSD, percentage relative standard deviation.

Table 2. System suitability parameters

S. No	Parameter*	Saxagliptin	Dapagliflozin
1	Theoretical Plate Count	2593	4843
2	Average Peak Area	56445	320903
3	Peak Height	6857	25250
4	RT	2.347	5.086
5	Tailing	1.41	1.18
6	Resolution	-	11.53
7	S/N	3128	482

*Average of 6 replicates.

Table 3. Recovery study

Analyte	Accuracy level	Peak area*	Amount added (mg)	Amount found (mg)	% Recovery	Mean % Recovery
Saxagliptin	50%	28244.7	5	5.01	100.26	100.36
	100%	56457.3	10	10.02	100.20	
	150%	85035.3	15	15.09	100.61	
Dapagliflozin	50%	161058.3	10	10.04	100.39	100.64
	100%	323719.3	20	20.18	100.89	
	150%	484374.0	30	30.19	100.64	

*Mean of three determinations at each level

Table 4.Precision study

Injection	Intraday Precision		Interday Precision	
	Area for Dapagliflozin	Area for Saxagliptin	Area for Dapagliflozin	Area for Saxagliptin
Average of 6 replicates	318150.7	56281.3	317963.5	56490.0
Standard Deviation	2457.0	172.6	1359.9	419.8
%RSD	0.8	0.3	0.4	0.7

Table 5. Linearity data

Linearity Level	Saxagliptin		Dapagliflozin	
	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Peak Area	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Peak Area
50	10	17896	20	132359
75	20	37780	40	223105
100	30	56233	60	320315
125	40	74754	80	419173
150	50	93611	100	526461
Slope	1884		4921	
Intercept	466.4		29001	
R^2	0.999		0.999	

Table 6. Robustness data

S. No	Parameter	Condition	SAXAGLIPTIN			DAPAGLIFLOZIN		
			RT	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing	RT	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Flow	0.9	3.2 73	3067.03	1.29	6.6 31	5361.12	1.16
2		1.0	2.3 40	2589.12	1.44	5.0 81	4825.77	1.19
3		1.1	2.0 24	2526.15	1.27	4.5 64	4766.36	1.13
4	Mobile phase- Organic content	10% less	2.7 55	3078.29	1.19	5.5 38	4573.25	1.11
5		Actual	2.3 40	2589.12	1.44	5.0 81	4825.77	1.19
6		10% more	1.9 74	2521.39	1.19	4.6 83	4756.36	1.12

Table 7. Forced degradation study

Sample Name	Dapagliflozin			Saxagliptin		
	Area	% Assay	% Degraded	Area	% Assay	% Degraded
Acid	295636	92.33	7.67	54275	96.52	3.48
Base	302783	94.56	5.44	52453	93.28	6.72
Peroxide	289767	90.49	9.51	53967	95.97	4.03
Thermal	316254	98.76	1.24	51867	92.24	7.76
Photo	286735	89.55	10.45	50162	89.2	10.80